
Ranked Behavioral Parameter	Loading Score
Step Cycle	0.399142259
Stand	0.389324683
Body Speed	-0.382419013
Regularity Index	-0.348733742
Swing	0.325143062
Social Recognition	-0.309003863
Stride Length	-0.288490011
Tail Suspension	0.268601947
Forced Swim	0.211578421
Novel Object Recognition	-0.141109552

Ranked Behavioral Parameter	Loading Score
Novel Object Recognition	0.612348247
TailSuspension	-0.442607264
Social Recognition	0.380965435
Stride Length	-0.367558391
Regularity Index	-0.269224633
Stand	0.168964398
Body Speed	-0.136769883
Step Cycle	0.117962471
Forced Swim	-0.108576196
Swing	-0.058768987

"What are loading scores in PCA?"

Positive loadings indicate a variable and a principal component are positively correlated: an increase

e in one results in an increase in the other. Negative loadings indicate a negative correlation. Large

(either positive or negative) loadings indicate that a variable has a strong effect on that principal c

omponent."